

Perspectives on Participating in Research Co-production

Evaluation of the co-production approach of the JUsT Solutions To Impacts of Climate Exposures for Health in Alaska (JUSTICE-HIA) project

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our deepest gratitude to all members of the team including faculty and staff from the University of Alaska Anchorage, University of Alaska Fairbanks, University of Washington, Swinomish Indian Tribal Community, partners from several Alaska communities (Igiugig, Galena, communities in the Copper River region, Fairbanks, and Anchorage Health Department), and representatives of statewide organizations (State of Alaska Department of Health, Alaska Native Tribal Health Consortium, Alaska Fire Science Consortium).

Funding

This work was supported by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency Assistance Agreement No. 84047901 awarded to University of Alaska Anchorage (Principal Investigator: Micah Hahn). It has not been formally reviewed by EPA. The views expressed in this document are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the Agency.

Suggested Citation

Loyd T (2025). Perspectives on participating in research co-production: Evaluation of the co-production approach of the JUsT Solution To Impacts of Climate Exposures for Health in Alaska (JUSTICE-HIA) project. Institute for Circumpolar Health Studies, University of Alaska Anchorage.

Project Principal Investigator:

Micah Hahn

mbhahn@alaska.edu

Institute for Circumpolar Health Studies

University of Alaska Anchorage

Table of Contents

- I. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY..... 4
- II. BACKGROUND..... 4
- III. PROJECT DESCRIPTION..... 4
 - Funding and Project Title..... 4
 - Project Partners..... 5
 - Project Goals..... 5
- IV. CO-PRODUCTION APPROACH..... 6
 - Co-production Definition and Framework..... 6
 - Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Justice, Accessibility (DEIJA) Definition..... 6
 - Team Communication..... 6
 - Group Commitments..... 7
 - Structure of Workshops..... 7
- V. CO-PRODUCTION EVALUATION..... 8
 - Evaluation Components..... 8
 - Analysis Approach..... 9
- VI. FINDINGS..... 9
 - Pulse Checks..... 9
 - Post-Workshop Surveys..... 10
 - Closing Reflections..... 11
 - Meeting Observations..... 11
 - Mid-Project Feedback..... 11
 - Group Interviews..... 11
- VII. DISCUSSION AND LESSONS LEARNED..... 12

- Appendix A: Pulse Check questions..... 14
- Appendix B: Example post-workshop survey..... 17
- Appendix C: Research Team member feedback form..... 19
- Appendix D: Group interview guide and sample Project Team member reflections..... 20
- Appendix E: Project Team Members..... 23

I. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The JUSTICE-HIA project (JUsT Solutions To Impacts of Climate Exposures for Health in Alaska) embedded co-production as a core principle from the outset. The primary goal of the project was to develop online climate and health data tools for Alaska communities. To ensure this process was inclusive and accountable, the project team wrote co-production activities directly into the grant proposal, adopted DEIJA (Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Justice, and Accessibility) values as guiding principles, and engaged an independent evaluator to monitor progress and help the team adjust and refine its approach over time.

Evaluation findings show that intentional design choices, such as shared group commitments, in-person workshops, support for Community Liaisons, and built-in feedback loops, helped translate co-production from intent to practice. Participants described the process as *“the most engaging project team I’ve ever been a part of”* and valued the opportunity to *“create something with whole people.”* Areas for improvement included providing more contextual grounding for out-of-state researchers and co-defining projects with partners earlier in the process. Team turnover was noted but effectively managed.

This report highlights practical methods for structuring collaborative research that supports meaningful participation, advances equity, and improves the usability of results. Lessons from this project offer a roadmap for applying co-production principles in future collaborations among Indigenous communities, researchers, and agencies.

II. BACKGROUND

This report was produced as part of JUSTICE-HIA (JUsT Solutions To Impacts of Climate Exposures for Health In Alaska), a U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) STAR-funded research project (Grant #840479) awarded to the University of Alaska Anchorage (UAA) with co-investigators from the University of Alaska Fairbanks and University of Washington (referred to hereafter as the “Research Team”).

The “Project Team” included: representatives of statewide organizations (Alaska Department of Health, Alaska Native Tribal Health Consortium, Alaska Fire Science Consortium), rural communities (Igiugig, Galena, and Copper River region), urban communities (Fairbanks, Anchorage Health Department), a collaborator from Swinomish Indian Tribal Community to provide support for the Indigenous Health Indicators component of the project, and graphic artists from 80% Studios to design and illustrate one of the project’s final products.

Agnew Beck Consulting was hired to help design and evaluate the co-production process. This role included observing in-person and virtual meetings, conducting surveys during and after workshops, interviewing team members, and providing feedback to the Research Team to continuously strengthen and improve equitable co-production throughout the project. This iterative evaluation was included in the grant proposal and funded through the grant as an integral component of the co-production process.

III. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Funding and Project Title

This project was funded through a U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) Science to Achieve Results (STAR) grant (R840479) awarded to the University of Alaska Anchorage, with co-investigators from the University of Alaska Fairbanks and the University of Washington. The official project title is *Filling data gaps: Development of a community-centered tool for assessing health impacts of intersecting climate hazards, wildfire smoke exposure, and social disparities in rural tribal and aging communities in Alaska.* To make the project easier to reference with

partners, the team adopted a shorter working title: JUsT Solutions To Impacts of Climate Exposures for Health in Alaska (JUSTICE-HIA).

Project Partners

The JUSTICE-HIA project involved three main groups of participants: Community Liaisons, State and Other Agency Representatives, and the Research Team. Collaborating organizations and communities were identified during proposal development, and specific representatives were identified after the project was funded.

- **Community Liaisons** included one to three representatives from each of three rural Alaska communities.
- **State/Agency Representatives** included one to three staff members from state, municipal, and Tribal organizations.
- The **Research Team** consisted of faculty and research staff from the University of Alaska Anchorage, University of Alaska Fairbanks, and University of Washington, along with invited guests who participated in specific project components.

Together, these groups formed the **Project Team**, which encompassed all researchers and partners. Some turnover occurred during the project period, largely due to normal employment transitions. A complete list of participants is provided in Appendix E.

Project Goals

The long-term goal of the JUSTICE-HIA project was to reduce negative health impacts from exposure to climate hazards in Alaska communities by improving access to locally relevant climate and social data to support adaptation planning. The overall objective was to co-develop community-centered tools for assessing the complex interrelated challenges of increasing exposure to wildfire smoke in the context of other climate-related stressors and existing social vulnerabilities. The project aims articulated in the proposal included:

- 1) Develop science community and stakeholder partnerships to co-design and co-produce the project
- 2) Co-develop statewide, web-based tool on climate-related exposures, social vulnerability, biomedical health indicators, and Indigenous health indicators
- 3) Demonstrate and showcase the co-developed tool's application through wildfire smoke-focused use cases

IV. CO-PRODUCTION APPROACH

Co-production Definition and Framework

The team defined **co-production** as a process that brings together multiple knowledge systems, including Indigenous, scientific, practitioner, and artistic perspectives, to generate new insights and understandings that would not emerge from any single system alone.

The **Co-Production of Knowledge (CPK) framework** (Figure 1) illustrates this process. At the center is the shared goal of the research. Surrounding it are interactive knowledge systems, working in partnership. The **inner ring** represents the key actions that drive a CPK research process, while the **outer ring** depicts the guiding concepts and principles that participants apply throughout the work.

Co-production is understood as an iterative and cyclical process, not a linear one, with equity encompassing all components of the framework.

Figure 1. A framework for co-production of knowledge. Source: Ellam Yua, J. Raymond-Yakoubian, R. Aluaq Daniel, and C. Behe (2022). A framework for co-production of knowledge in the context of Arctic research. *Ecology and Society* 27(1):34.

Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Justice, Accessibility (DEIJA) Definition

At the project kick-off meeting, the Research Team introduced the concepts of **Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Justice, and Accessibility (DEIJA)** as a shared framework (Figure 2). Because this terminology was familiar to most participants, it provided a useful starting point for conversations about how co-production principles would be applied in practice. The DEIJA framework also guided the evaluation, with these concepts used as key themes for coding and analyzing feedback data, as described in later sections.

Figure 2 (shown to the right). Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Justice, Accessibility (DEIJA) framework as introduced at the start of the JUSTICE-HIA project to the team.

Team Communication

The Project Team communicated through a combination of in-person workshops, online meetings, and email between gatherings. Five full-day, in-person workshops were held at the University of Alaska Anchorage, scheduled immediately after environmental conferences that already brought many participants to Anchorage from Fairbanks and rural communities. Aligning workshop days with existing travel commitments helped reduce time and cost burdens, particularly for Community Liaisons traveling from communities off the road system. Out-of-state Research Team members traveled from Seattle to participate in the workshops.

Group Commitments

At the project kickoff meeting, participants collaboratively developed **Group Commitments** to establish shared expectations and guide how the team would work together (Table 1). These commitments were revisited at the start of each workshop, and Project Team members were invited to reflect on how well the group was upholding them during each gathering.

Table 1. Group commitments for JUSTICE-HIA as developed by the Project Team at the project’s kickoff meeting

<p>Inclusive meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Limit lectures and instead elevate conversation and activities aimed at gathering diverse perspectives ● Create opportunities for all communication styles, including providing time for self-reflection; make space for others to speak/contribute ● Provide for varied participation opportunities (phone-in or no-video) for remote meetings ● Accommodate everyone’s schedules for remote meetings (e.g. consider breaking meetings up over several days) ● Record remote meetings for those who are unable to attend ● Leave space in meetings to get to know one another on a personal level
<p>Clear communication between meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Utilize email subject line with expected response deadlines ● Use a one-pager update for the purpose of members sharing externally to others (e.g. bosses) ● Be transparent with information: all team members should have access to all the materials that they want/need, without being inundated with unnecessary details
<p>Setting clear expectations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Measure progress towards goals and sharing the results with team ● Make sure each team member has a designated role, and knows their role ● Incorporate clear expectations, roles, and next “action” steps with deadlines into our meeting notes ● Start our meeting agendas with “objectives for the day”
<p>Collaboration and respect</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Be prepared and organized so that our time is of value ● Follow through on commitments, or let other team members know you can’t complete tasks by established deadlines ● Credit the team for work rather than taking credit individually ● When interacting with communities, make sure someone known to the community is involved in the interaction ● Acknowledge that language is very important: all participants should understand what is to be done before it is done ● Listening to all perspectives and incorporating those perspectives into solutions
<p>Creating a useful and accessible tool</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create a just tool by being aware of barriers and removing them wherever possible ● Keep sustainability of the tool in mind and connecting with people who can help distribute the tool to a wider audience ● Make sure we aren’t duplicating efforts in creation of our tool; bring back any duplicative efforts we notice to the team ● Leverage everyone’s unique skills, knowledge, talents, and services in creating the tool in order to make it our own

Structure of Workshops

The five workshops were designed with transparent and flexible agendas, shared facilitation, and a mix of presentations, group discussions, and hands-on activities. Over time, the schedule became more adaptable, allowing sessions to run with some flexibility while still closing on time. This approach helped participants engage fully in discussions, trusting facilitators to guide transitions when needed.

Workshops began with icebreakers to help participants get to know each other as whole people, often focusing on favorite foods, recipes, or subsistence traditions. Food played a central role in the workshops, with meals and snacks thoughtfully planned to reflect local businesses, participant preferences, and dietary needs. Participants frequently noted the value of these shared meals, appreciating both the quality of the food and the opportunity to connect socially around the table.

V. CO-PRODUCTION EVALUATION

Agnew Beck Consulting was hired to design and evaluate the co-production process. Their role included observing in-person and virtual meetings, conducting surveys during and after workshops, interviewing team members, and providing feedback to the Research Team to continuously strengthen equitable co-production practices. This iterative evaluation was included in the grant proposal and funded as an integral component of the project. The evaluator worked closely with the Research Team to co-design evaluation components that offered multiple ways for Project Team members to provide feedback and delivered practical, timely insights that could be used to improve workshops and the overall project process.

Evaluation Components

Evaluation activities were embedded into workshop structures:

- **Pulse Checks** – Real-time, anonymous feedback was collected twice per workshop using Slido. Each Pulse Check included a single Likert-scale question followed by time for open reflection. Research Team members typically abstained from responding to avoid bias, as they had designed the workshop agendas. (See Appendix A for questions and responses.)
- **Post-Workshop Surveys** – After each workshop, all team members completed a written survey via SurveyMonkey. Questions (approximately ten per survey) included both multiple choice and open-ended formats, with minor variations depending on the workshop’s focus. Time was built into the workshop for completion, resulting in near 100% participation. (See Appendix B for an example post-workshop survey.)
- **Closing Reflections** – Each workshop ended with an opportunity for an optional oral reflection. Prompts typically encouraged participants to share “something I learned or something I will take away from the workshop.” These reflections complemented written survey responses and provided a sense of closure for the day.

In addition to pulse checks, post-workshop surveys, and closing reflections, three additional components were part of the evaluation:

- 1) **Meeting Observations** – The evaluator attended all in-person workshops and a subset of virtual meetings, observing tone, physical space, pace, meals, language, engagement, and attendance.
- 2) **Mid-Project Feedback** – The evaluator collected feedback from Research Team members midway through the project to assess ongoing participation and engagement from Project Team members between workshops (See Appendix C for mid-project feedback survey)

- 3) **Closing Group Interviews** – At the end of the project, the evaluator conducted group interviews to gather general feedback and lessons learned from Project Team members. (See Appendix D for interview guide and sample Project Team reflections).

Analysis Approach

After each workshop, the evaluator entered all open-ended participant responses, both oral and written, as well as observations on tone, physical space, pace, meals, language, engagement, and attendance, into a spreadsheet (Table 2). Each entry was tagged with the source (Research Team, Community or State/Agency Liaison, or Evaluator), the relevant DEIJA principle it reflected, length of participation in the project, and workshop number.

Multiple-choice survey responses were also analyzed, with trends tracked across workshops. Following each workshop, the evaluator shared findings with the Research Team and facilitated discussions to provide recommendations for adjusting future workshops in response to feedback and emerging patterns.

Table 2: Snapshot of the DEIJA Values Mapping spreadsheet (SM: SurveyMonkey, post-workshop survey tool; AB: Agnew Beck, independent evaluator employer)

Method	Response	Diversity	Equity	Inclusion	Justice	Accessibility	Workshop	Team
AB: Engagement	Note-at 10am (one hour in) most people giving full attention-one laptop open per table (for notes) and two phones active (of 20 people).			x			5	Evaluator
Debrief reflections (spoken)	Feel like I am meeting whole people-not just someone who does art and someone who does data, but whole people: people, expertise, every aspect of all the people.		x				5	Research
SM: How would you compare your JUSTICE-HIA experience being part of this project to other projects?	I feel like it is a lot of work to organize these meetings, but it is so worth it. I haven't been to another project meeting that I thought integrated community and researcher perspectives to this extent.			x			2	State/other
SM: As we begin to wrap up our time together on this grant, is there anything else you would like to share about the experience?	I am sure based on our level of communication now that we will continue to communicate and network in the future.					x	5	Community Liaison

VI. FINDINGS

Feedback from the JUSTICE-HIA project evaluation was overwhelmingly positive and consistently attributed to the intentional co-production practices embedded throughout the project.

Pulse Checks

The pulse checks were effective in providing immediate, actionable insights to the team and helped participants share feedback in real time. They took less than 10 minutes, including time for sharing verbal reflections at the end. They were particularly valuable for creating opportunities for voices that might otherwise be quieter to be heard. One Community Liaison reflected:

I appreciated the check-ins, pulse checks. Yup 'ike people are quiet and wait for others to be done and then pause before talking, so often I don't get to say what I want to say. Having these opportunities helps overcome that barrier and helps people feel heard.

Overall, participants reported feeling engaged and supported, and the pulse check feedback allowed the Research Team to make timely adjustments during workshops. For example, if participants indicated only a basic understanding of a topic covered earlier in the day, facilitators could spend additional time reviewing it to ensure clarity and comprehension.

Example pulse check question:

- I understand how my unique perspective enhances this project.
- 0%: I am not certain how my perspective is unique and feel others have more to offer in this process than I do.
 - 33%: I am not certain how my perspective is unique but feel my contributions are/can be impactful.
 - 33%: I am aware of the unique perspective I bring to this process but do not feel I make/can make significant impact in this process.
 - 33%: I am aware of the unique perspective I bring to this process and feel my contributions are/can be impactful.

See Appendix A for additional pulse check questions.

Post-Workshop Surveys

Post-workshop surveys effectively captured participants' reflections while experiences were still fresh and provided the Research Team with actionable insights for future sessions. The evaluator compiled survey responses and shared findings with the team after each workshop. Feedback helped guide adjustments by addressing questions such as: Were topics given sufficient time and attention? Did participants feel heard and represented? Was the group functioning cohesively toward shared goals?

Overall, responses indicated that participants felt their voices were represented, topics were covered adequately, and the group worked cohesively. Constructive feedback almost always included practical suggestions, which were incorporated into subsequent workshops.

Example post-workshop survey question:

- Our activities and discussions are meant to provide opportunities to get to know one another better and to enhance comfort with sharing ideas and opinions. Which of the following most closely reflects the level of comfort you feel with this team as a result of today's activities and discussions?
- 90%. This meeting provided sufficient opportunities to get to know team members better. I am very comfortable expressing my ideas and opinions in this group.
 - 10%. This meeting provided sufficient opportunities to get to know team members better. I am beginning to feel more comfortable expressing my ideas and opinions in this group.
 - 0%. Although I am comfortable expressing my ideas and opinions in this group, I would [have] appreciate[ed] more opportunities to get to know my team members better.
 - 0%. Having more opportunities to get to know one another better would [have] increase[ed] my comfort in expressing my ideas and opinions in this group.

See Appendix C for an example post-workshop survey.

Closing Reflections

Oral reflections provided a space for participants to share personal takeaways and reinforced the written survey feedback. Participants consistently highlighted the value of getting to know each other as whole people and expressed enthusiasm for future gatherings.

Closing reflections indicated strong group cohesion and a high perceived value of the workshop time, often ending the sessions on a positive, celebratory note. Many participants noted that the JUSTICE-HIA project was a favorite team experience amid their busy and often hectic work schedules.

Meeting Observations

Evaluator observations during Project Team gatherings provided a rich, qualitative perspective on workshop dynamics that complemented surveys and reflections. By attending workshops in full and taking detailed notes on interactions, body language, engagement, presence, and group dynamics, the evaluator captured insights that might not be apparent through written feedback alone. This method allowed the Research Team to see how co-production practices were functioning in real time and to make informed adjustments as needed.

For the JUSTICE-HIA project, these observations confirmed that participants were engaged, felt supported, and actively used multiple avenues to share feedback. They also highlighted positive group dynamics, strong participation, and opportunities for iterative improvements in workshop facilitation. Detailed notes were integrated with pulse checks, post-workshop surveys, and closing reflections to track the success of co-production practices over the course of the project.

Mid-Project Feedback

The mid-project feedback survey of the Research Team was designed to capture reflections on how Community Liaisons were experiencing support between workshops and how effectively co-production principles were being implemented outside of formal meetings. The survey captured reflections on the frequency, type, and format of support requests from Community Liaisons, participation in virtual meetings and community events, adherence to group commitments, and the experience of researchers serving in a supportive rather than leading role. Open-ended questions allowed team members to share additional observations or suggestions for improving collaboration.

For the JUSTICE-HIA project, survey responses indicated that all groups were functioning well. Community Liaisons felt comfortable requesting support when needed and deferring it when other responsibilities were higher priority. Feedback also suggested that the balance of researchers in a support role worked effectively, regardless of differences in team composition or experience levels.

Group Interviews

Group interviews provided a structured opportunity to capture team reflections on overall dynamics and the effectiveness of co-production, offering insights that might not emerge during workshops or surveys. By convening participants in virtual group interviews, the evaluator was able to explore how co-production influenced collaboration, outputs, and participant experiences.

For the JUSTICE-HIA project:

- **Research Team:** Mid-level and junior researchers who had actively contributed to workshop planning and facilitation, but were not Principal Investigators, were asked to participate in this

interview. Reflections highlighted that project outputs differed meaningfully from what would have been produced without co-production. As one participant put it:

Products that came of the project were different than they would have been without all co-production. Feels like [the fact that] outputs were so different from what was proposed is quite good evidence that this was co-produced work.

- **State/Other Agency:** Participants represented a range of agencies and experience levels. Reflections highlighted the value of considering tool usability and accessibility to ensure outputs would be practical and shareable for end users. As one participant noted:

I appreciated the experience. I didn't leave the project with a different understanding of wildfire/ smoke, but it did provide time to step back and think about who will be using the tools- access, barriers for those people. We approached [building tools] in a way to ensure the people can use and can share them with others.

- **Community Liaisons:** While a virtual group interview was not possible due to busy schedules and the summer subsistence season, their post-workshop survey responses provided insight. One participant wrote:

Successful effort of co-production. This experience is very inclusive and collaborative, I always feel seen and heard working on this project. The commitments and values were always upheld; this has been one of the most thoughtful and engaging collaborations I have participated in.

Across all groups, oral and written reflections demonstrated that the project was considered worthwhile, that community work was meaningful and likely to be carried forward, and that the co-production process was both valued and effectively upheld.

VII. DISCUSSION AND LESSONS LEARNED

The JUSTICE-HIA project demonstrated that intentional co-production practices can create meaningful, inclusive, and productive research experiences. Participants from all three teams, Community Liaisons, State/Other Agency representatives, and the Research Team, consistently expressed appreciation for the shared work, time together, and the deliberate efforts to incorporate all voices and perspectives.

Lessons learned from the engagement process

Key elements that supported successful co-production included:

- *Structured and intentional participation:* Group Commitments, DEIJA definitions, and clear articulation of co-production principles provided a shared framework for collaboration.
- *Flexible, accessible workshop design:* Hosting in-person workshops aligned with existing travel plans, incorporating icebreakers, local food, and opportunities for informal connection fostered trust and relationship-building.
- *Ongoing support:* Offers of continued support from Research Team and State/Other Agency members helped Community Liaisons feel supported without pressure.
- *Iterative feedback integration:* Ongoing mechanisms for feedback from the Project Team informed real-time adjustments to workshops and project activities.

Participants noted that these practices created a strong foundation for future collaboration and expressed interest in projects that explicitly prioritize co-production.

Lessons learned from the evaluation process

Reflections on elements of the evaluation process included:

- *Independent evaluation adds value:* Engaging an external evaluator provided a neutral perspective to track co-production practices, identify opportunities for improvement, and give timely feedback to the team.
- *Multiple feedback channels are critical:* Combining real-time pulse checks, post-workshop surveys, oral reflections, and group interviews captured a range of experiences and allowed participants to share feedback in the way that worked best for them.
- *Practical insights guide adaptation:* Evaluation findings supported workshop adjustments and informed team practices, highlighting areas such as group dynamics, engagement, and equitable participation.

Opportunities to strengthen future co-production efforts

Participants highlighted several ways future projects could enhance co-production practices:

- *Sustaining co-production practices:* Develop strategies to ensure that co-production principles and DEIJA values actively guide collaboration throughout the project and are reinforced in future work beyond the project's formal end.
- *Building contextual understanding:* Provide opportunities for all team members to deepen their knowledge of local communities, cultural practices, and regional priorities, supporting collaboration and ensuring research outputs are relevant and usable.
- *Co-design from the start:* Whenever possible, involve collaborators in project design before funding is finalized to strengthen alignment, shared ownership, and commitment.
- *Managing team transitions:* Anticipate turnover and maintain representation from communities, agencies, and universities to ensure continuity, inclusivity, and sustained engagement.

Overall, the JUSTICE-HIA project illustrates that co-production is a practical and meaningful approach to applied research. By recognizing lived experience alongside scientific and technical expertise, teams can create outputs that are both usable and relevant. While we continue to learn and refine our practices, sharing these experiences may help other teams work toward more inclusive, equitable, and responsive co-production in their own projects.

Appendix A: Pulse Check questions

Workshop 1: None conducted

Workshop 2, Morning

I understand how the tool we are developing will benefit rural Alaska communities.

1. I have a solid understanding of the benefits of this tool for our rural Alaska communities. At this point, I could easily describe many benefits to others.
2. I have a good understanding of the benefits of this tool for our rural Alaska communities. At this point, I could describe several benefits to others.
3. I have a basic understanding of the benefits of this tool for our rural Alaska communities. At this point, I could briefly describe one or two benefits to others.
4. I am just beginning to understand the benefits of this tool for our rural Alaska communities. At this point, I would not be able to describe these benefits to others.

Workshop 2, Afternoon

I understand how my unique perspective enhances this project.

1. 0%: I am not certain how my perspective is unique and feel others have more to offer in this process than I do.
2. 33%: I am not certain how my perspective is unique but feel my contributions are/can be impactful.
3. 33%: I am aware of the unique perspective I bring to this process but do not feel I make/can make significant impact in this process.
4. 33%: I am aware of the unique perspective I bring to this process and feel my contributions are/can be impactful.

Workshop 3, Morning

I understand how Indigenous Health Indicators (IHIs) and community dialogues can be used to benefit rural Alaska communities.

1. I have a solid understanding of the benefits of IHI community dialogues for our rural Alaska communities. At this point, I could easily describe many benefits to others.
2. I have a good understanding of the benefits of IHI community dialogues for our rural Alaska communities. At this point, I could describe several benefits to others.
3. I have a basic understanding of the benefits of IHI community dialogues for our rural Alaska communities. At this point, I could briefly describe one or two benefits to others.
4. I am just beginning to understand the benefits of IHI community dialogues for our rural Alaska communities. At this point, I would not be able to describe these benefits to others.

Workshop 3, Afternoon

I am feeling comfortable leading (or supporting) community dialogue(s) given the framework and support we have been offered today.

1. I am feeling very comfortable leading community dialogue(s) given the framework and support we have been offered today.
 2. I am feeling comfortable leading community dialogue(s) given the framework and support we have been offered today.
 3. I am beginning to feel comfortable leading community dialogue(s) given the framework and support we have been offered today.
 4. I do not feel comfortable leading community dialogue(s) given the framework and support we have been offered today.
-

Workshop 4, Morning

I feel that my voice was heard in the development of our two tools as they stand now.

1. I am feeling very heard.
2. I am feeling heard.
3. I am beginning to feel heard.
4. I am not feeling heard.

Workshop 4, Afternoon

I understand how our work together (IHIs and/or the two online tools) can be used in my work/community.

1. I have a solid understanding of how our work together can be used in my work/community.
 2. I have a good understanding of how our work together can be used in my work/community.
 3. I have a basic understanding of how our work together can be used in my work/community.
 4. I am not understanding how our work together can be used in my work/community.
-

Workshop 5, Morning

I understand how the user guide scenarios can support the use of the online tools we have developed to benefit Alaska communities and feel like I am contributing to the development of the user guides.

1. I have a solid understanding of the goal of the user guide scenarios and feel like I am contributing a lot to the development of the user guides.
2. I have a good understanding of the goal of the user guide scenarios and feel like I am contributing to the development of the user guides.
3. I have a basic understanding of the goal of the user guide scenarios and feel like I am contributing a little to the development of the user guides.
4. I do not understand the goal of the user guide scenarios and I am not contributing to the development of the user guides.

Workshop 5, Afternoon

I see a user guide scenario that is relevant to my personal experience and/or work environment, and I feel clear about how I can apply it.

1. My lived experience (personal or professional) is very well represented by the user guide scenarios, and I very clearly see how I can apply this.
 2. My lived experience (personal or professional) is represented by the user guide scenarios, and I see how I can apply this.
 3. My lived experience (personal or professional) is somewhat represented by the user guide scenarios, and I may be able to apply this.
 4. My lived experience (personal or professional) is not represented by the user guide scenarios, and I do not see how I can apply this.
-

Appendix B: Example post-workshop survey

Shared with the Project Team after the final workshop. Questions stayed largely uniform across workshops, modified slightly to address specific workshop goals.

Q1a: Which group of participants do you identify as a member?

Q1b: How long have you been a part of this project team?

Q2: The information shared during the presentations- 1) Reminder of Wildfire Explorer Tool and updates, 2) Review goal of user guides process and intro story, 3) updates to Northern Climate Reports tool- provided the foundation for today's discussions and small group activities. Which of the following most closely reflects your understanding of this information?

- The presentations were clear and easy to follow. I understood the concepts well enough to engage in subsequent activities and discussions.
- Although the presentations were not always clear or understandable for me, I had the basic information needed to engage in subsequent activities and discussions.
- The presentations often lacked the clarity I needed to fully engage in later activities and discussions.

Q3: Is there anything we can do after this workshop to help you share information about the Wildfire Explorer or Northern Climate Reports tools in your community or workplace?

Q4: Our activities and discussions are meant to provide opportunities to get to know one another better and to enhance comfort with sharing ideas and opinions. Which of the following most closely reflects the level of comfort you feel with this team as a result of today's activities and discussions?

- This meeting provided sufficient opportunities to get to know team members better. I am very comfortable expressing my ideas and opinions in this group.
- This meeting provided sufficient opportunities to get to know team members better. I am beginning to feel more comfortable expressing my ideas and opinions in this group.
- Although I am comfortable expressing my ideas and opinions in this group, I would [have] appreciate[ed] more opportunities to get to know my team members better.
- Having more opportunities to get to know one another better would [have] increase[ed] my comfort in expressing my ideas and opinions in this group.

Q5: Team members were selected to ensure a broad range of perspectives, knowledge and expertise. Everyone's voice is important. Which of the following best represents your experience of group discussions?

- I had ample opportunities to express my ideas and opinions and felt they were fairly considered.
- I had ample opportunities to express my ideas and opinions but did not always feel they were fairly considered.
- I did not have/take much opportunity to express my ideas and opinions but felt they were fairly considered when I did.
- I did not have/take much opportunity to express my ideas and opinions and did not always feel they were fairly considered when I did.

Q6: As we think about future projects, what can we do differently to ensure your voice, or the voice of those you represent in the capacity you joined this team, is heard and considered? Was there anything that prevented you from talking or made you feel your voice was not heard?

Q7: The objectives for this meeting were identified as follows: 1) Dive into the user guide scenarios for the Wildfire Explorer tool! Further develop the narratives, create the story elements, and work with the artists to begin sketches. 2) Review updates to the Northern Climate Reports tool and learn about the “how-to” video production process. Which of the following best represents your sense of what we accomplished?

- The goals and objectives were realistic; the team accomplished all or most of what we set out to do.
- The goals and objectives were realistic; however, the team accomplished only some of what we set out to do.
- The goals and objectives were overly ambitious for the time we had; however, the team still accomplished all or most of what we set out to do.
- The goals and objectives were overly ambitious for the time we had; the team accomplished only some of what we set out to do.

Q8: Our group commitments are meant to ensure our meetings reflect the values of diversity, equality, inclusion, justice and accessibility that form the foundation of how we operate as a team. Referring to the slide, how do you think our group commitments and values were reflected in this meeting?

Q9: How would you compare your JUSTICE-HIA experience being part of this project to your experience being part of other projects?

Q10: As we begin to wrap up our time together on this grant, is there anything else you would like to share about the experience? Please feel free to reflect on this experience overall, your likelihood of continued professional engagement with new people you met throughout this time together, the experience of being asked to come in person for these workshops, the effort at connection points in between, your thoughts on explicitly trying to cultivate co-production in a process like this, or anything else on your mind.

Appendix C: Research Team member feedback form

Presented as Google Doc to be contributed to over the summer during collaborative project work.

1. How often does your Community Liaison (CL) reach out for support?

- What type of support is requested? Please include specific language from the Community Liaison.
- How quickly is the support offered and in what format?
- Do you know your CL's preferred format for engagement? Have you been able to match that?
- If they do not reach out, how often have you initiated contact and in what ways?

2. How many virtual meetings were held between in-person workshops?

- Who attended? (Everyone who RSVPed or fewer people than planned?)
- How did group members participate (keep DEIJA values in mind as you share reflections).

3. Did anyone from the Research Team join the planned community events in person?

- If so, please share impressions that would contribute to co-production framing.

4. Are group commitments being upheld through these months of engagement?

- If yes, please point to specific examples.
- If no, please share challenges.

5. Given that this co-production effort is placing the researchers in more of a support role than a lead role with the IHI process, please share your reflections on that experience.

6. Open-ended thoughts.

Appendix D: Group interview guide and sample Project Team member reflections

Interview Guide (modified slightly per group):

1. What does “co-production” mean to you, and how well do you think it was practiced in this project?
2. Thinking back to the beginning of your participation, did you feel comfortable engaging with the co-production process as an explicit element of the project? Was that something you had experienced before?
3. Of the groups involved in the project, how would you describe the role of your team? Was it clear, comfortable, and meaningful from your perspective?
4. Was there any resistance in getting approval to work on the project or motivating yourself to prioritize it given that there was not a clear outcome stated at the beginning (since the point was to develop the final work together)?
5. What was the experience of representing your community either solo or as a member of a small team that attended the workshops?
6. Were there any pleasant surprises? How about expected or unexpected obstacles?
7. How has this project influenced your work or perspective about using data for decision-making? Through this work, do you think about wildfire smoke or wildfire differently? How about the use of data to make decisions about events?
8. Are there ways that co-production altered the course of what you would have expected for the final products? How so?
9. If another community were starting a similar partnership, what would you tell them?
10. What should future research teams definitely do or avoid doing based on your experience?
11. What is the likelihood of your looking for jobs or projects that will allow for this kind of co-production in the future? What would make you want to participate in co-produced project in the future?
12. Is there anything else you would like to share?

Research Team (oral) sample responses:

- Successful effort at co-production. “Everyone felt like an equal partner, voices heard, voiced their thoughts, sharing knowledge, coming from different points of view.” And “it felt really natural to me, made complete sense.”
- Definition of co-production “western knowledge and traditional knowledge coming together.”
- Stronger co-production could only have come if all partners could have been present at the conception of the project. “Workshops successful, people enjoyed them, heard all voices, no one

excluded. But at the end of the day, this was still a research project that communities helped with rather than something [communities] brought to us.

- Products that came of the project were different than they would have been without all co-production. “Feel like [the fact that] outputs were so different from what was proposed is quite good evidence that this was co-produced work.”
- Appreciated the experience. “I was personally comfortable and professionally uncomfortable which is kind of the point. If [things are] super comfortable and going like normal, probably co-production is not happening.”
- Likely to seek out co-production opportunities in the future and to continue collaborations with new colleagues from the project. “Happy and excited to work with anyone on this project again.”

State/Other Agency (oral) sample responses:

- Successful effort at co-production. “Love the collaboration, emphasis on having time to figure things out, not being so reactive, hearing thoughts. This way of collaborating was a stark difference from the State and that’s why I liked it so much.” And “as best as possible, intentional, great.”
- Definition of co-production. “Co-production is building relationships.” And “inviting/involving people from actual communities to identify needs and how to get there- rather than going in to say, here is what we are doing and what do you think?”
- Stronger co-production could have come from explicitly enforcing the values set a bit more. “There were times when I thought a few people talked a little bit too much when they probably should have stepped back to listen- would have liked to see that value enforced a little bit more. Could have reminded them [research team member] of positionality and how to be good at listening.”
- Products that came of the project were different than they would have been without all co-production. “Wasn’t expecting an art component, made it so much better, visualizing something was very fun and refreshing.” And “came away from the workshop thinking about data sovereignty and how that needs to be addressed at the State level.”
- Appreciated the experience. “I didn’t leave the project with a different understanding of wildfire/smoke, but it did provide time to step back and think about who will be using the tools- access, barriers for those people. We approached [building tools] in a way to ensure the people can use and can share them with others.”
- Likely to seek out co-production opportunities in future and to continue collaborations with new colleagues from the project. “Liked how we felt in the space. Helped with building relationships for future work because we made those connections and relationships.”

Community Liaison (written) sample responses:

- Successful effort of co-production. “This experience is very inclusive and collaborative, I always feel seen and heard working on this project.” And “the commitments and values were always upheld; this has been one of the most thoughtful and engaging collaborations I have participated in.”
- Definition of co-production. “The way we move our dialogue and tweak our dialogues together- in person, deep dive, cultural and lived experience- will miss this. This was fun. A joy.” And “much more active participation” than experiences being part of other projects.
- Stronger co-production could have come from more balance with the Research Team. “Hard to identify with some out of state researchers who didn’t understand life in Alaska and Tribal communities.” And “way more researchers than community members.”

- Products that came of the project were different than they would have been without co-production and will be useful going forward. “Appreciative of the support and work from research team, as a community it feels good to know people care about what is happening to us. Not every project builds in time for relationship building and knowing where we come from- want to bring IHIs forward and everything we’ve learned.” And “I continue to enjoy the long-term support and collaborative nature of the project. I believe it will result in effective and pragmatic resources for rural AK communities.”
- Appreciated the experience. “Grateful to be here, if you told 5yr old me you’d be in a workshop with researchers creating something useful one day, I’d be like what? Dreams are hard to go for where I am from, we see people being stuck where they are, maybe someday my daughter could use this tool.”
- Likely to seek out co-production opportunities in the future and to continue collaborations with new colleagues from the project. “I’m going to miss being a part of this group. I’m excited to see the finished website/app. I hope we can work together again in some sort of capacity.” And “Yes, the [connections beyond this project] already have happened and I hope they continue!”

Appendix E: Project Team Members

Project Team members organized by role in the Project Team (shown alphabetically by organization and then by first name). When roles shifted (as happened with some State/Other Agency team members), the former employer is listed as well.

Name	Institution	Job Title	Project Role
Research Team			
Micah Hahn	University of Alaska Anchorage Institute for Circumpolar Health Studies	Associate Professor of Environmental Health	Principal Investigator
Nancy Fresco	University of Alaska Fairbanks International Arctic Research Center	SNAP Network Coordinator	Co-Principal Investigator
Nicole Errett	University of Washington Environmental and Occupational Health Sciences	Assistant Professor	Co-Principal Investigator
Tania Busch Isaksen	University of Washington Environmental & Occupational Health Sciences	Associate Teaching Professor	Co-Principal Investigator
Melissa Bradley	University of Alaska Anchorage Institute for Circumpolar Health Studies	Research Professional	Research Associate
Muhammad Khan	University of Alaska Anchorage Institute for Circumpolar Health Studies	Research Professional	Research Associate
Nelsha Athauda	University of Alaska Anchorage Institute for Circumpolar Health Studies	Research Professional	Research Associate
Theresa Vertigan	University of Alaska Anchorage Institute for Circumpolar Health Studies	Research Professional	Research Associate
Mike DeLue	University of Alaska Fairbanks International Arctic Research Center	Science Communicator	SNAP team
Anna Reed	University of Washington Environmental & Occupational Health Sciences	Research Coordinator	Research Associate

Cat Hartwell	University of Washington Environmental & Occupational Health Sciences	Research Coordinator	Research Associate
Mariana Cortes Espinosa	University of Washington Environmental & Occupational Health Sciences	Graduate Student	Research Associate
Community Liaisons			
Colleen Merrick	Copper River Native Association	Climate Change Coordinator	Community Liaison
Amber Shumpert	Fairbanks North Star Borough	Emergency Preparedness Coordinator	Community Liaison
April Hostetter	Igiugig Village Council	Tribal Stewardship and Yup'ik Language Program Co-Director	Community Liaison
Mary Hostetter	Igiugig Village Council	Tribal Steward and Igiugig Village Council Board Member	Community Liaison
Bill Kane	Igiugig Village Council and Alaska Venture Fund	Tribal Stewardship Director; Program Manager	Community Liaison
Brooke Sanderson	Louden Tribal Council	Tribal Administrator	Community Liaison
Tirzah Bryant	Louden Tribe (Galena)	Environmental and Education Coordinator	Community Liaison
Derrick Sinyon	Native Village of Gakona	Environmental Coordinator	Community Liaison
Lishaw Lincoln	Native Village of Gakona	Environmental Assistant	Community Liaison
State Liaisons			
Alison York	Alaska Fire Science Consortium	Coordinator	State/Other Agency
Amy Brown	Anchorage Health Department Environmental Health	Environmental Health Educator	State/Other Agency
Andrew Willman	ANTHC Air and Healthy Homes Program	Senior Program Manager	State/Other Agency
Melissa Castaneda	ANTHC Air and Healthy Homes Program	Program Manager	State/Other Agency

Oxcenia O'Domin	ANTHC Air and Healthy Homes Program	Tribal Environmental Program Associate	State/Other Agency
Abby Nelson	ANTHC Center for Climate and Health (Previously State of Alaska)	Public Health Program Specialist	State/Other Agency
Sarah Yoder	ANTHC Center for Climate and Health (Previously State of Alaska)	Program Manager	State/Other Agency
Other Contributors			
Jamie Donatuto	Swinomish Indian Tribal Community & University of Washington Environmental & Occupational Health Sciences	Clinical Associate Professor	Guest Researcher
Casey Silver	80% Studios	Co-founder	Guest Artist
Dimi Macheras	80% Studios	Co-founder	Guest Artist
Bruce Crevensten	University of Alaska Fairbanks International Arctic Research Center	Technical Lead	SNAP team
Josh Paul	University of Alaska Fairbanks International Arctic Research Center	Geospatial Data Analyst	SNAP team

ANTHC: Alaska Native Tribal Health Consortium